

Study of the Results of the Cholesterol Profile Associated with Patients Suffering from Rheumatoid Arthritis in Iraqi Patients

Dr. Murooj Luai Majeed Altimimi

Assistant Professor in Pharmacology in the Pharmacology Department in Kufa Medical College, Al-Najaf, Iraq

Dr. Firas Hameed Abd Alsafi

M.B.Ch.B., CABM. Med., FICMS. Cardio, Ministry of Health, Baghdad Medical office Al-Karkh, Ibn Al-Bitar Center for Cardiac Surgery, Adult Cardiology Department, Baghdad, Iraq

Annotation: The objective of this study was to assess the cholesterol profile outcomes in rheumatoid arthritis patients who were recruited from different hospitals over a period of time that ran from December 2022 up to October 2023.

A total of one hundred patients were selected and allocated into two groups, which comprised 80 patient' groups and 20 control groups. As per the mean value and standard deviation, the ages of the patients were $30.3 + 4.4$ for the patient group and $29.2 + 3.3$ for the control group.

In this study, there was a significantly higher proportion of male patients (62.5%) compared to female patients among a cohort of 50 individuals.

The researchers analyzed data and results regarding patients and a control group using IBM SOFT SPSS as well as Microsoft Excel version 2013 to come up with the findings of the present study. The present study showed that the majority ages were between eighteen to thirty years old, while there was a higher prevalence among male patients (62.5%).

Regarding comorbidities, they had different distributions in accordance to blood pressure, where heart disease had the highest occurrence among seventeen people. In addition, the atherogenic index of rheumatoid arthritis progressively increases with disease activity, resulting into a significant relationship between them ($p < 0.05$), hence leading to an off-scale cholesterol profile associated with these kinds of disorders.

The correlation between cholesterol and RA remains uncertain. However, it is hypothesized to stimulate immune cells, stimulate the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and contribute to the development of atherosclerosis, a buildup of plaque in arteries associated with RA.

Rheumatoid arthritis patients show increased cardiovascular disease rates due to functional limitations, with total cholesterol and LDL-C values significantly higher in RA patients compared to controls but lower in HDL-C patients.

Keywords: Cholesterol profile, HDL, LDL, Patients, RA.

Introduction

However, individuals with rheumatoid arthritis RA, a chronic inflammation condition, really have about two to three times increased risks of cardiovascular diseases than those who don't have the disease [1;2,3;4]. In this respect, it has been identified that chronic inflammation associated with diseases, physical inactivity, elevated body fatness, insulin resistance, and altered lipid profiles are the main culprits [5;6]. Although their risk of developing cardiovascular disease (CVD) is increased, persons with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) usually show reduced total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) levels. With RA patients, "the lipid paradox" has been attributed to a decrease in the concentration of bile salts [7,8,9]. This paradox

is inversely correlated with disease activity and the degree of coronary artery calcification. In chronic inflammatory disorders, anti-inflammatory treatment may lower the chances for CVD due to a rise in lipid quantities as a result of decreased inflammation and slowing down the metabolism of esterified cholesterol [10,11,12].

A recent American study revealed that cholesterol-lowering drugs, called statins, can reduce the number of deaths resulting from rheumatoid arthritis by 33%. [13,14]

The researchers indicated that statin drugs can reduce the risk of death from arthritis diseases, including ankylosing spondylitis, which causes stiffness in the spine and other joints, and rheumatoid arthritis. [15]

To reach the results of the study, the research team analyzed the results of a database from Britain, which included 5,808 patients with rheumatoid arthritis who began treatment between the years 2000-2014. Half of the patients used cholesterol-lowering drugs, while the other half never used these drugs. [16]

our study aims to assessment outcomes of the cholesterol profile associated with patients suffering from rheumatoid arthritis in Iraqi patients.

Material and method

Data collection

A cross-sectional study was designed in Iraq from several different hospitals, and 80 patients were collected in this study.

Our study objective is to evaluate the results of the cholesterol profile in Iraqi patients with rheumatoid arthritis.

Study design

The study design was observational, descriptive, and cross-sectional and was based on patients regularly treated in the autoimmune disease service at several different hospitals. From December 2022 to October 2023, we conducted a pilot study to ascertain the expected frequency necessary for calculating the sample size. To this end, according to inclusion and exclusion criteria, 80 patients were evaluated, and 80% were found to have dyslipidemia. In addition, it was determined that the total number of patients coming to the clinic monthly was approximately 50, with an accuracy level of 95% and a strength of 80%.

The inclusion criteria were age > 18 years and diagnosis of rheumatoid arthritis.

Exclusion criteria were the presence of primary dyslipidemia, secondary to medications, metabolic disorders, or other diseases that alter the lipid profile.

Patients with rheumatic diseases other than rheumatoid arthritis. Before rheumatoid arthritis, patients with mixed connective tissue disease received a diagnosis of dyslipidemia.

Ten patients with type 2 diabetes were among the 80 patients who visited the clinic during the study period, while five patients chose not to participate. In total, 80 patients agreed to be part of the study and signed informed consent, allowing them to participate in it.

The patient's age and sex were among the data entered on the recording sheets.

We divided age into four periods: 18 to 30, 31 to 45, 45 to 60, and over 60 years. We then recorded the weight, height, and body mass index. The WHO classification was used: underweight (<18.50), normal (18.50 to 24.99), overweight (25 to 29.99), obese grade 1 (30 to 34.99), obese grade 1 (35 to 39.99), and obese. Third degree (> 40.00)

After fasting for 9 to 12 hours, we took blood samples for lipid analysis. 5 ml of blood was drawn from the bend of one elbow, and lipid analysis involves measuring levels of HDL-C, LDL-C, total

cholesterol, and triglycerides. We determined the values of the first three components mentioned using enzymatic colorimetric methodology to find LDL-C,

Aim of study

The main aim here is assessing the cholesterol profile findings among Iraqi patients suffering from rheumatoid arthritis.

Results

Table 1- Demographic results of patients

Variable	Value
Age	
18 to 30, F (P%)	30 (37.5)
31 to 45 F (P%)	17 (21.25)
45 to 60 F (P%)	20 (25)
Over 60 years F (P%)	13 (16.25)
SEX	
Male F (P%)	50 (62.5)
Female F (P%)	30 (37.5)
Comorbidities	
blood pressure F (P%)	33 (41.25)
Diabetes F (P%)	10 (12.5)
Heart disease F (P%)	17 (21.25)
Other diseases F (P%)	10 (12.5)
Education	
Primary	9 (11.25)
Secondary	29 (36.25)
College	25 (31.25)
High	7 (8.75)
Smoking (%)	
Yes	18 (22.5)
No	62 (77.5)
BMI	
MEAN \pm SD	30.93 \pm 3.12
Causes of rheumatoid arthritis	
Genetic causes	10 (12.5)
age	20 (25)
Sex	15 (18.75)
Obesity	35 (43.75)
Symptoms of rheumatoid arthritis	
Joint Pain	9
Swelling	10
Stiffness	14
Fatigue	14
Joint Warmth and Redness	10
Limited Range of Motion	11
Deformities	12

Table 2- Demographic results of control

Variable	Value
Age	

18 to 30, F (P%)	5 (25)
31 to 45 F (P%)	4 (20)
45 to 60 F (P%)	2 (10)
Over 60 years F (P%)	9 (45)
SEX	
Male F(P%)	10 (50)
Female F(P%)	10 (50)
Comorbidities	
blood pressure F(P%)	7 (41.25)
Diabetes F(P%)	4 (12.5)
Heart disease F(P%)	5 (21.25)
Other diseases F(P%)	4 (12.5)
Education	
Primary	3 (15)
Secondary	5 (25)
College	8 (40)
High	4 (20)
Smoking (%)	
Yes	5 (25)
No	15 (75)
BMI	
MEAN \pm SD	27.1 \pm 2.86

Fig 1- Comparison of outcomes HDL cholesterol between healthy and patients

Fig 2- Comparison of outcomes LDL cholesterol between healthy and patients

Fig 3- Comparison of outcomes Triglycerides between healthy and patients

Fig 4- Comparison of outcomes Total cholesterol between healthy and patients

Table 3- Logistic regression to analyze risk factors in patients with rheumatoid arthritis

	Rheumatoid Arthritis		
		AOR (95%CI)	P-value
Sex	Male	1.1 (0.77-1.23)	
	Female	1.987 (1.44-2.5)	0.002*
Age (years)	18 to 30	0.88 (0.55-1.3)	0.98
	31 to 45	1.3 (0.89-1.88)	0.04
	45 to 60	2.2 (1.65-2.9)	0.001
	Over 60 years	4.4 (3.66-6.8)	<0.0023*
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.9–29.9	1.87 (1.55-3.1)	0.05
	>29.9	4.4 (3.22-6.6)	<0.001
Comorbidities			
blood pressure		2.3 (1.5-3.3)	0.09
Diabetes		3.5 (1.9-4.4)	<0.001
Heart disease		1.5 (1.2-1.9)	0.01

Table 4- Evaluation of the quality of life of patients compared with the control group

Variable	Patients	Control	P-value
Anxiety	54.4±6.6	34.4±3.4	0.01
Depression	61.2±4.3	44.2±3.3	0.003
The psychological aspect	58.4±2.7	37.8±4.98	<0.002*
Social side	55.87±2.2	39.9±4.55	0.001
pain	56.6±3.1	35.5±2.7	<0.01

Discussion

A cross-sectional study was conducted in Iraq to find out the Results of the cholesterol profile associated with patients suffering from rheumatoid arthritis in Iraqi patients.

In this study, patients were distributed into two groups (80 patients and a control group of 20 patients).

The most frequent ages in this study were 18 to 30 years for 30 patients (37.5), followed by 45 to 60 years for 20 patients (25), followed by 31 to 45 years for 17 patients (21.25%), Over 60 years for 13 patients (16.25%)

In this study, the prevalence of male patients was greater than that of female patients in a group of 50 patients with (62.5%)

In Table 1, patients were distributed according to comorbidities (blood pressure) for 33 patients with (41.25%), heart disease 17 patients (21.25%).

It was also found that the body mass index of the patient group was higher compared to the control group, as the body mass index of the patient group was according to the true value and the arithmetic mean.

30.93±3.12 as for the body mass index of the control group, it was 27.1±2.86, as shown in Table 2.

In our study, there were more male patients. This may be explained by the higher prevalence of rheumatoid arthritis in this group, although the incidence of dyslipidemia was the same in both sexes. The percentage of women and men is approximately equal to that reported in the study by Cisternas et al.

Cholesterol profile in rheumatoid arthritis appears to depend on disease activity. According to a review of previous articles, the total cholesterol value and the HDL-C value are lowered more if there is greater activity leading to a higher atherosclerosis index. However, statistical significance was found between disease activity and Lipid Profile [17,18].

Patients with rheumatoid arthritis are characterized by functional limitations that lead to increased rates of cardiovascular disease, and statistical relationships have been found between total cholesterol and LDL-C values with functional impairment. [19]

Rheumatoid arthritis is primarily caused by cardiovascular system pathology, with atherosclerosis playing a significant role in its development. Both diseases are immune-inflammatory, with a close relationship and new treatment possibilities. Rheumatoid arthritis is associated with changes in blood lipids, leading to increased arterial stiffness. Anti-inflammatory treatment can decrease rheumatoid arthritis activity and atherosclerosis coefficient. Active patients with rheumatoid arthritis experience increased total and LDL cholesterol levels, increasing arterial stiffness and cardiovascular risk. [20,21]

The study found significant increases in hs-CRP and TC concentrations among RA patients compared to controls but lower HDL-C concentrations. This is due to decreased anti-inflammatory activity of HDL-C, which is an independent predictor of future cardiovascular risk complications, and a decrease in HDL-C levels indicates a higher likelihood of complications.

Conclusion

The study findings revealed that there was a significant increase in total cholesterol (TC), TC/HDL, and LDL/HDL levels, as well as a decrease in HDL-C levels for individuals who were suffering from rheumatoid arthritis compared to the control group. This relation to disease activity turns out to be significant at a p-value of 0.01.

The relationship between cholesterol and RA is not clear yet, but it is proposed that it may activate immune cells, induce the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines, and promote the development of atherosclerosis, which is the accumulation of plaques in arteries that is linked to RA.

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